

White Paper

Task Force 3: Interactions with the external environment

Topic A:

Smart buildings as flexibility providers to the electricity grids

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Document information

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Executive summary

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating issues related to smart buildings: their objective is to identify the remaining challenges and barriers to smart building deployment, and the associated research and innovation gaps that should be addressed in the near future.

Task force 3 investigates how smart buildings can interact at best with their external environment. The first topic addressed by this task force and presented in this paper is the smart buildings as provider of flexibility to the electricity grids.

Within the European Commission's strategy to reach a climate neutral Europe in 2050, the integration of more renewable electricity into the power grids constitute a key pillar. But a higher penetration of renewables into the electric grids constitutes a challenge, due to the intermittent and hardly predictable nature of some renewable energy sources – such as wind and solar – and the technical constraints of the existing electricity networks. Consequently, capturing the flexibilities offered within the energy system (flexibilities in generation, demand and storage) constitutes a significant lever to enable the integration of more RES at lower operational cost.

While demand side mechanisms are already operational to exploit flexibilities in the industrial sector, buildings from the commercial and residential sectors are still far from being used at their full flexibility potential. Today, smart technologies enter more and more into those buildings, providing new means to capture the power system flexibility potential offered by equipment and end-user behaviour, with added value both for the building users and the grid. However, this flexibility potential is spread among myriads of buildings, each being source of a small amount of flexibility. Convergence is therefore required to exploit the full flexibility potential of this segment.

Therefore, this white paper addressed the following questions:

- **To what extent can buildings contribute to serving the flexibility needs of the grid?**
- **How should such services be valued so that building end-users show interest and have benefits in using them?**
- **How to facilitate the further implementation of building's flexibilities on a technical, organisational, and contractual standpoint?**

In its first part, this paper provides a state of the art regarding the following issues, specific attention being paid to EC-funded projects:

- **Definitions and requirement** regarding the provision of power flexibility by smart buildings
- **The status of deployment of smart metering and demand response in Europe**
- **Data standards and interoperability aspects**, with a focus on the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM), the needs for alignment among the communication standards from the Utility, Telecom and Home appliances industries in order to reach semantic¹ interoperability, and the recent developments by the BRIDE working group regarding a reference architecture for European energy data exchange and a methodology to study the interoperability of flexibility assets
- The **Harmonized Electricity Market Role Model** to facilitate the dialogue between the electricity market participants and recommendations for its further development, as well as the **USEF framework for market design** to support distributed flexibilities, implementing the European Commission's electricity market directive

¹ Semantic interoperability: understanding of the concepts contained in the message data structures

- **The Workflows and processes enabling grid flexibility services**, including the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), and labels such as Ready2Service 4GRIDS or GOFLEX.

A brainstorming process enabled to identify some key barriers and drivers regarding the deployment of power flexibility services by buildings. The next diagrams provide an overview of the main barriers and drivers discussed.

Figure 1: Overview of main barriers

BARRIERS	
ECONOMIC	Lack of viable business models that really incentivize and remunerate the building occupants
VALUE CHAIN	Lack of readiness of industrial players including grid operators
	Lack of technical and economic scalability of technologies (too customised, heavy human interventions required)
	Lack of standardization among smart devices and how they are modeled
REGULATION	GDPR and data privacy issues
	Heterogeneity of national regulatory frameworks with regards to electricity markets and end-user participation
SOCIAL	Lack of awareness of the functionalities and benefits of a grid-interactive building by the building end users
TECHNICAL	Lack of interoperability of solutions as of today

} *Top barriers according to the Task Force*

Figure 2: Overview of main drivers

DRIVERS	
VALUE CHAIN	Strong requirements faced by grid operators to integrate more renewable electricity in the grid, coupled with new types of loads (e-V) providing new flexibility sources
REGULATION & STANDARDS	Regulation allowing the development of local energy communities, self-consumption, demand-side flexibility
	Regulatory constraints on data interoperability, transparent data access, data privacy, that will ensure privacy-friendly energy data exchange
ECONOMIC	Financial incentives such as dynamic tariffs for consumers or the increase of CO2 emission rights price
	Smart buildings becoming an investment opportunity for non-financial actors, such as private persons or companies
SOCIAL	The willingness of citizens to reduce their environment impact (from active consumer, to prosumer, to energy communities)
TECHNICAL	New means and opportunities offered by communication automation & control technologies (from end user phone, to home appliances, to RES/storage devices, to smart grid)
	The ongoing development and demonstration of interoperability-focused architectures, paving the way to standardization (connect any smart appliance to any service)

} *Top drivers according to the Task Force*

Based on the State of the Art and the barriers and drivers, a number of research and innovation gaps were identified. They are synthesised in the next two diagrams.

Figure 3: R&I gaps

Figure 4: "Go-to-market" gaps

The gaps identified above will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

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List of abbreviations

BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BIM	and Building Information Modelling
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand Side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
eVs	Electric Vehicles
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TF	Task Force

1. Introduction

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating topics related to smart buildings. They respectively address the interaction between building and end-user, efficient building operation, interactions between the building and the external environment, and cross cutting issues.

Figure 5: The four Task Forces set up by the SmartBuilt4EU project

SmartBuild4EU task force 3 investigates how the smart building can interact with its external environment in a mutually beneficial way. The first line of investigation is **TOPIC A: Smart buildings as providers of flexibility to the electricity grids**

The present White Paper presents the outcomes of a collective work carried out by the members of the Task Force, from March to June 2021. Paced by series of online workshops, the following steps were addressed:

- Definition of scope
- Review of the State of the Art and identification of the points to be investigated in particular
- Analysis of barriers and drivers
- Identification of R&I gaps.

The final aim of this White Paper is to feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

2. Topic under investigation by the Task Force

2.1. Rationale

Within the European Commission’s strategy to reach a climate neutral Europe in 2050, the integration of more renewable electricity into the power grids constitute a key pillar. But a higher penetration of renewables into the electric grids constitutes a challenge, due to the intermittent and hardly predictable nature of some renewable energy sources – such as wind and solar – and the technical constraints of the existing electricity networks. Consequently, capturing the flexibilities offered within the energy system (flexibilities in generation, demand and storage) constitutes a significant lever to enable the integration of more RES at lower operational cost.

While demand side mechanisms are already operational to exploit flexibilities in the industrial sector, buildings from the commercial and residential sectors are still far from being used at their full flexibility potential. Today, smart technologies enter more and more into those buildings, providing new means to capture the power system flexibility potential offered by equipment and end-user behaviour, with added value both for the building users and the grid. However, this flexibility potential is spread among myriads of buildings, each being source of a small amount of flexibility. Convergence is therefore required to exploit the full flexibility potential of this segment.

Therefore, this white paper aims to provide an overview of what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- To what extent can buildings contribute to serving the flexibility needs of the grid?
- How should such services be valued so that building end-users show interest and have benefits in using them?
- How to facilitate the further implementation of building’s flexibilities on a technical, organisational, and contractual standpoint?

2.2. Scope

Based on the key questions identified in the previous section, four main blocks of knowledge are deemed most relevant to identify pathways towards the increase of flexibility provision by smart buildings.

Figure 6: The four building blocks of Topic A

Quantification of the power flexibility potential of smart buildings and the related services to the grid

- **Flexibility assessment:** how to assess the overall flexibility potential of buildings, how to measure the actual flexibility provided to the grid? To what extent can flexibility services contribute to grid investment deferrals?
- **Single building vs building blocks:** what is the role of individual buildings vs the role of blocks of buildings in achieving a flexible power grid (Multi-Building Energy Management Approach)
- **Respective roles of stakeholders involved:** what are the roles of building owners, building operators and occupants in enabling interaction with the grid and managing/optimizing flexibility? Which role for aggregators?

Business models that remunerate the value of building flexibility to the end-users

- **Economic and contractual models:** how can the value of flexibility be captured by the end-user, fostering its engagement in demand response?
- **What should be the exact role of aggregation** in such models?

Technologies and processes enabling grid flexibility

- **Convergence and integration of technologies** and services to provide building-to-grid flexibility: what is the optimal level of integration?
- **Use of 'external' data sources** such as multi - Scale Interoperable Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) for flexibility service purposes
- **Certification framework:** how to check the compliance of buildings to provide flexibility ("ready to service" "ready to grid") and how can the smart readiness indicator (SRI) contribute to this?
- **Standards** to allow scaling up of Demand Response solutions.

Fully interoperable data exchange environment to provide power flexibility to the grid

- **Data environment and interoperability:** which specific data needs to be exchanged in order to enable flexibility services? What are the interoperability issues specific to the provision of flexibility services to the grid?
- **Digital twin:** how to consider this concept development in the specifications of data requirements?

More generic interoperability questions are covered by Task Force 2 (Efficient Building Operation) in its first White Paper: Interoperability of smart building solutions.

3. State of the Art

As stated by the JRC in its technical report on smart home and appliances², there are three interrelated areas where ICT is expected to have an impact on the efficiency of energy systems, in accordance with the Digital Single Market strategy:

- **Buildings** - in the form of building management systems and sensor networks
- **Energy Grids** (Smart Grids) – in order to reduce peak demand and potentiate integration of renewable sources
- **Households** – with the introduction of smart meters and smart appliances, making consumers aware of their energy consumption and potentiate behavioural change.

3.1. Definitions

Which definition should be used to define the object of study, i.e. the smart building in its dimension of interactions from the end-users to the electricity grid?

² Smart home and appliances: State of the art. JRC Technical Report, 2019.

1. The US Department of Energy defines the **grid-interactive efficient building (GEB)**³ as: *“an energy efficient building with smart technologies characterized by the active use of distributed energy resources to optimize energy use for grid services, occupant needs and preferences, and cost reductions in a continuous and integrated way.”* In this definition, grid-interactive buildings combine four key attributes: energy efficiency, renewable energy, energy storage, and load flexibility. The cross-optimisation of those four attributes results in a less peaky, more flexible energy load profile which reduces operational costs, largely through demand charge savings.

2. Wang, Huilong & Wang, Shengwei & Tang, Rui (2019)⁴ define the **“grid-friendly and grid-responsive building”** where:

- **Grid-friendly** means that a building can work in synergy with the power grid and avoid putting additional stress on the balance of the power grid, and
- **Grid-responsive** means that a building can respond to the needs and requests of the smart grid, contributing to the grid power balance timely and effectively, in order to enhance the reliability of the power grid and optimize the overall efficiency of the grid-building ecosystem.”

This second definition seems more generic and inclusive but is missing the dimension of **optimal relationship between the building’s end-users and the electricity grid**. The above definition could therefore be completed with a third point:

- **End-user-engaging** means that a building enables and fosters through smart solutions the engagement of final end-users in responding to the needs and requests of the smart grid.

To complement these definitions, we owe to mention the **SMART 2016/0082 study**⁵ on demand side flexibility which defines:

- **Demand-side flexibility** as “the ability to change electricity output or demand in reaction to an external signal”
- **Demand Response** as « the change of electricity load by final customers from their normal or current consumption patterns in response to market signals, including time-variable electricity prices or incentive payments, or in response to acceptance of the final customer's bid, alone or through aggregation, to sell demand reduction or increase at a price in organised markets as defined in Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 1348/2014 ».

Demand Response programmes are broken down in two categories:

- **Implicit Demand Response** refers to consumers choosing time-varying electricity prices and/or time-varying network tariffs that partly reflect the value or cost of electricity and/or transmission and distribution in different time periods. These prices are part of their supply contract, and consumers do not participate in a market.
- **Explicit Demand Response** participates to the wholesale, balancing, ancillary services and capacity markets through the services of aggregators or single large consumers. Consumers receive direct payments to change their consumption upon request. They can earn from their flexibility in electricity consumption individually or by contracting with an aggregator, which can either be a third-party or the customer’s retailer.

³ Grid-interactive Efficient Buildings Technical Report Series, DoE, 2019

⁴ “Development of grid-responsive buildings: Opportunities, challenges, capabilities and applications of HVAC systems in non-residential buildings in providing ancillary services by fast demand responses to smart grids”, Applied Energy, May 2019

⁵ Study on ensuring interoperability for enabling Demand Side Flexibility, TNO, DNV-GL, ESMIG for the EC, 2018

3.2. Use cases and requirements for the grid-interactive building

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) released some Smart grid requirement within the IEC 62913 series. Part 2-3 focuses on Resources connected to the grid. In the IEC deliverable, several Smart Building use-cases are listed, together with the associated system requirements and level of maturity.

Those use cases are:

- Adapt the smart building behaviour to the energy manager/client preferences
- Enable the interoperability between the smart building and the smart grid
- Manage flexibility on electricity demand & generation within the smart building from market signals and from emergency signals
- Provide enriched Smart Building data to relevant parties in order to make the energy manager/client more active
- Value the flexibility of the smart building

The New Building Institute⁶ identifies the key technological requirements for energy efficient Grid-interactive buildings as follows:

Requirement	Target	Present status
Interoperability and intelligence from building to grid	Grid-interactive buildings should receive utility price signals and share the availability of flexible loads within the building to modulate loads and optimize for cost, carbon, reliability, and other factors.	Even buildings engaged in curtailment or demand response programs do not often have an automated process, and virtually no buildings automatically shift loads based on real-time changes in utility price signals.
Interoperability and intelligence across building systems	Grid-interactive buildings should have a unified, overarching, and intelligent system that controls HVAC, lighting, plug loads, thermal or electric storage, and other key building loads.	Many building loads (e.g., plug loads) are seldom controlled at all, let alone to optimize to utility price signals. Existing control systems vary widely across building type, size, and vintage, but most building controls are not set up to coordinate across building systems.
Load flexibility and demand-focused optimization	Grid-interactive buildings should have the intelligence to track building demand, predict patterns that can help limit peak demand, and shift or shed demand rapidly in response to grid or building events.	Using the same functions to limit building billing peak is often more cost-effective than responding to narrow DR events. The ability to predict weather patterns, track renewable energy generation curves, or predict building operational needs can allow a grid-interactive building to limit monthly peaks and reduce costs more than today's more traditional efficiency- and demand response-focused energy management practices.

Figure 7: Technological requirements for energy efficient Grid-interactive building as defined by the New Building Institute

See White Paper “Interoperability of smart building solutions” of Task Force 2 (Efficient Building Operation) for definitions on interoperability.

⁶ See *The Value of Grid-Interactive Buildings to Building Owners*, New Building Institute, 2019

3.3. Overview of State of the Art

Deployment of smart metering

A broad implementation of smart meters is one of the most important steps towards a smart built environment and energy system. Smart meters monitor real-time data on energy use allow communication with other devices (e.g. other smart meters, appliances, servers...). On the one hand they allow building occupants to gain awareness and have an active role in the control of their energy consumption. On the other hand, they are a key component of a smart grid. The JRC report on smart appliances summarizes the state of play in Europe as follows⁷:

- The legislation for electricity smart meters is in place in most Member States. Only five countries have no such legislation in place.
- Sixteen Member States will proceed or have already proceeded to large-scale roll-out of smart meters. In Poland and Romania, the Cost Benefit Analysis yielded positive results but official decisions on roll-out are still pending
- In seven Member States, the Cost Benefit Analysis for large-scale roll-out by 2020 were negative or inconclusive, but in Germany, Latvia and Slovakia smart metering was found to be economically justified for particular groups of customers.

Deployment of Demand Response framework

According to BPIE⁸, demand response is generally available for industry, but not yet for commercial and residential sectors. The Joint Research Center (JRC) report on Demand Side flexibility⁹ identifies three key factors for the deployment of demand response:

- the definition of independent aggregators to ensure the consumer's right to choose their energy service provider and allow full aggregation of consumer's loads
- market designs that enable the participation of DR and other distributed resources
- technical modalities enabling DR that are defined by standardization and replication throughout whole Europe.

The same report maps a “three-speed-Europe” about the regulatory status of Member States concerning Demand Response:

- A set of Member States that have not yet adjusted their regulatory structures to enable demand side resources to participate in the markets, nor begun the process of defining the role of an independent aggregator and DR service provider.
- A second group of Member States more advanced on the enablement of DR (Austria, Finland, Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden) by enabling DR through the energy retailer. The retailers in these Member States offer a “bundle packaged offer” with their electricity bill, which the consumer can only accept or refuse entirely, with some lack of transparency.
- The third group of Member States enables both Demand Response and independent aggregation: Belgium, France, Ireland and the UK. Belgium and France have both defined the roles and responsibilities around independent aggregation. To that third group, the Smart Energy Demand Coalition¹⁰ adds Finland, as the country allows independent aggregation in at least ancillary service

⁷ Source: JRC Technical Report on Smart Appliances

⁸ BPIE. 2017. Is Europe ready for the smart buildings revolution?

⁹ Demand Response status in EU Member States”, JRC, 2015

¹⁰ Explicit Demand Response in Europe Mapping the Markets, SEDC 2017

programme and is experimenting through pilot projects with independent aggregation in other parts of the balancing market.

Numerous H2020 projects are investigating demand flexibility measurement and value, developing and demonstrating tools to enable DR at building level and its contribution to grid services. They are briefly introduced further below in section 3.4.

Building Energy Management Systems and Internet of Things

Building Energy Management Systems aim to increase the energy efficiency of operational buildings and ensure indoor comfort for building occupants, through the monitoring and active management of building devices thanks to building sensors and controls. The next diagram synthetises the different interactions that BEMS can cover.

Figure 8: General architecture of a BEMS for a Net-Zero energy building¹¹
 GW = Gateway

Internet of things (IoT) are now becoming a key component of modern BEMS, offering a set of low-power distributed intelligent sensors for monitoring different parameters of the building (temperature, lighting, humidity, air quality), different sorts of bidirectional communication technologies, and a wide range of actuators to implement controls on different building devices. Recent studies¹² show that IoT can support building energy management for five main applications: energy consumption control, predictive control for temperature regulation, sensing of residents’ comfort, integration of controllable devices and smart home applications.

A key pending issue regarding the deployment of these systems is related to data standards and interoperability, as elaborated upon below.

Status on data standards and interoperability

¹¹ Source: Intelligent Buildings in Smart Grids: A Survey on Security and Privacy Issues Related to Energy Management. Alvaro Llaría et al, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14092733>

¹² Yaïci, W.; Krishnamurthy, K.; Entchev, E.; Longo, M. Recent advances in Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructures for building energy systems: A review. Sensors 2021.

The SGAM (Smart Grid Architecture Model)- initially developed by CEN/CENELEC/ETSI and complemented by IEC in IEC TS 63200 - provides an architectural approach allowing for a representation of interoperability viewpoints in a technology neutral manner. It counts five interoperability layers (Business, Function, Information, Communication and Component) with the two dimensions of the smart grid plane, i.e. zones (representing the hierarchical levels of power system management) and domains (covering the complete electrical energy conversion chain).

Figure 9: Interoperability layers in the SGAM model, CEN-CENELEC-ETSI

TNO, ESMIG and DNV-GL produced in 2018 for the EC a **Study on ensuring interoperability for enabling Demand Side Flexibility (DSF)**, focusing on the residential sector (home appliances, not including storage). The report investigates the need for alignment among the communication standards from the Utility, Telecom and Home appliances industries, in order to reach semantic¹³ interoperability. Eight standards are compared using the reference ontology [SAREF](#) (Smart Appliances REference ontology) developed in a project commissioned by DG-Connect, and its extension for the energy domain, SAREF4ENER. The main findings of this study are as follows:

- A certain alignment already exists among the eight DSF standards against the SAREF/SAREF4ENER ontology, and full alignment is reachable:
 - The standards SPINE and oneM2M are fully aligned with SAREF/SAREF4ENER.
 - Four standards need further alignment, for which actions are defined.
 - The remaining two standards, CENELEC EN 50491-11 and IEC 61968-9 CIM for Metering, do not have a direct alignment with SAREF/SAREF4ENER, but are aligned through the COSEM standard, which covers the same interface.
- A proof of concept allowed to demonstrate the DSF interoperability through the complete, end-to-end IT infrastructure, from smart grid to smart meters and smart appliances.
- A set of recommendations is provided to build upon this proof of concept and align the standards.

¹³ Semantic interoperability: understanding of the concepts contained in the message data structures

Standard	Level of alignment	Alignment required
EN 50631-1 (SPINE)	Fully Aligned with SAREF/SAREF4ENER	No
oneM2M Base ontology	Fully Aligned with SAREF	No
IEC/CENELEC 62056 COSEM	Fair alignment with SAREF/SAREF4ENER	Yes
CEN 16836 (ZigBee SEP2)	Fair alignment with SAREF/SAREF4ENER	Yes
CENELEC EN 50090 (KNX)	Potential alignment with SAREF/SAREF4ENER	Yes
IEC 61970 CIM	Potential alignment with SAREF/SAREF4ENER	Yes
CENELEC EN 50491-11 Smart Metering	Aligned with IEC/CENELEC 62056 COSEM	No
IEC 61968-9 CIM for Metering	Aligned with IEC/CENELEC 62056 COSEM	No

Figure 10: The eight demand-side flexibility standards studied in the report

Several EU projects are currently addressing and testing the interoperable dimensions of smart solutions involving buildings in the smart grid (INTERCONNECT, PHOENIX, FLEXIGRID, PLATOON, detailed further below). The **BRIDGE working group** on data management developed a reference architecture for European energy data exchange¹⁴, using the SGAM model introduced above. The same working group also developed methodology to study the interoperability of flexibility assets, allowing to analyse the system implementation of flexibility-related use-cases by BRIDGE projects¹⁵. The report also provides recommendations.

Harmonised role model and USEF market design

ENTSO-E, EFET and ebIX developed the Harmonized Electricity Market Role Model¹⁶ to facilitate the dialogue between the electricity market participants from different countries through the designation of a single name for each role and domain within the market. A role model defines core responsibilities in a business sector. The clustering of roles per company depends on the regional/national regulation and on commercial business decisions. Specifying information exchange as exchange between roles therefore allows the reference core process model to support variations in regulation.

The role model was mainly developed to enable a common terminology for IT development, but it is also of interest for harmonized presentations of business cases and the conceptualization of new business models in relation to electricity markets.

The 2021 BRIDGE report on *European energy data exchange reference architecture* provides some recommendations for the further development of the role model:

- Propose to ENTSO-E, ebIX and EFET new roles and classes to be included and definitions to be adapted in existing role models.
- Harmonise data roles across electricity and other energy domains by developing the Harmonised Energy Role Model and look for consistency with other domains outside energy (cross-sectoral roles).

¹⁴ BRIDGE European energy data exchange Reference Architecture Report, April 2021

¹⁵ BRIDGE Interoperability of Flexible Assets Report, April 2021

¹⁶ The harmonised electricity market role model, ENTSO-E, EFET and ebIX, 2018

In addition, since 2015, USEF17 has worked on a new market design to support distributed flexibilities. This market design implements the European Commission’s electricity market directive and defines mainly:

- A Flexibility Value Chain, from customer needs to flexibility market and products
- A role model, built on top of the HEMRM to support this value chain, in which smart buildings are represented as Active Consumers
- An interaction model, focusing on the relationship between the Aggregator and the Supplier and BRP
- A protocol, USEF’s Flexibility Trading Protocol (UFTP), to support the information flows between the actors.

The USEF framework¹⁸ has been updated in May 2021 to take into account the feedback from the first implementations, in particular within the EU R&I projects (Horizon 2020 program).

Workflows and processes (certification...) enabling grid flexibility services

The EPBD sets out provisions to establish a “Smart Readiness Indicator” (SRI) as an instrument for rating the smart readiness of buildings. This optional common EU scheme will assess the technological readiness of buildings to interact with their occupants, to interact with connected energy grids and to operate more efficiently. Studies are ongoing to define and evaluate implementation pathways.

The smart readiness indicator (SRI) takes into account three main functionalities of the smart building:

- The ability to maintain energy efficiency performance and operation of the building
- The ability to adapt its operation mode in response to the needs of the occupant
- The flexibility of a building's overall electricity demand, including ***its ability to enable participation in active and passive as well as implicit and explicit demand-response, in relation to the grid, for example through flexibility and load shifting capacities.***

Some evaluation criteria in the methodology developed focuses on flexibility and grid integration.

There is a need for gap analysis on smart grid technical readiness of buildings. AIOTI¹⁹ recommends the inclusion of “network readiness” as a key impact criterion to address the importance of connectivity for smart systems to function smoothly.

Regarding labels, qualification and certification schemes, the table below provides an overview.

Labels and certification schemes	Short description
SmartScore	Global digital connectivity rating scheme (for offices and homes) Does not seem to cover the grid-connectivity dimension
Ready2Service 4GRIDS	French label based on a reference framework that sets out the requirements to be met by a Smart Building, an open and communicating building, ready for the services, including building flexibility
GOFLEX	New building energy flexibility index by GIMELEC (tool, not label or certification) Energy flexibility of buildings is defined as “their ability to be disconnected from the power network at the most appropriate time.”

Figure 11: Overview of labels and schemes related to smart grid readiness of buildings

¹⁷ <https://www.usef.energy/>

¹⁸ <https://www.usef.energy/app/uploads/2021/05/USEF-The-Framework-Explained-update-2021.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/AIOTI-SRI-Position-Paper-Final-for-Publication.pdf>

3.4. EU projects

BRIDGE²⁰ task force on R&I priorities analysed most H2020 ongoing projects dealing with grid flexibility. Among the projects identified, the following ones significantly integrate consumer/ prosumer device control and demand flexibility from buildings:

- **Ebalance Plus** addressed demand response and management of building devices via IoT-based systems. **FlexiGrid** developed in-home ICT technologies for smart appliances (e.g. smart load controllers) for direct control of consumer demand, incl. visualisation via in-home displays. **Netfficient** developed prosumer device control.
- In **InteGrid**, a home energy management system for domestic prosumers - was developed and demonstrated with over 50 residential users. Bi-lateral agreement schemes were applied with customers.
- In the **Inertia** project, automated control of building's assets (HVAC, lights and other appliances) was applied by the building subsystem. An Aggregator Control Hub managed to successfully provide the requested amounts of flexibility to the DSO.
- In **SMILE**, a load controller (aggregator platform) was able to control domestic heat installs, EV smart charging and large industrial load to support the local grid in increasing the demand side management capacity and reduce curtailment.
- **EU-SysFlex** performed some monitoring and control of residential flexibilities and of customer-scale and office-scale batteries. **FutureFlow** developed demand side management for commercial (and industrial) customers and control of distributed generation to provide aFRR ancillary services via device control.
- In **TILOS**, integrated, controllable loads were classified according to their elasticity to inform different DSM strategies. DSM functionalities were tested at the end-user level and in aggregate. Water pumps deemed as the most deferrable loads.
- In **Cultural-E project**, technologies and control strategies are combined at building level by a cloud-based Building Management System which leverages on load shifting, energy storage and predictive models to boost building-to-grid flexibility of Positive Energy Buildings.

In addition, our taskforce identified as well:

- EU projects **INTERCONNECT**, **AMBIANCE**, **Flexcoop**, **PHOENIX**, **HOLISDER**, **SENDER** investigate **Business models** to capture buildings flexibility. **AMBIANCE** and **Flexcoop** also investigate the role of the aggregator.

In terms of technical solutions related to building/grid power exchanges:

- **IFLEX** focuses on household consumers with the development of Intelligent Assistants for Flexibility Management, including grid-support services.
- **RESPOND** develops solutions to deliver demand response at a building unit, both at building and district level. **TALENT** develops solutions for battery control in multi-home buildings to provide flexibility.
- **MUSE GRIDS** investigates flexibility at both power and thermal grids level.
- **PHOENIX** will develop services for building owners and occupants to maximize their comfort and energy savings in existing buildings, as well as data analytics services to energy utilities.

²⁰ BRIDGE is cooperation group of Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands and Digitalisation H2020 projects: <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

- **INTERCONNECT** will develop solutions connecting smart homes, buildings and grids, and a marketplace of integrated digital platforms bridging the gap between IoT and energy.
- **TABEDE** will deliver technologies enabling buildings to implement demand-response without high investments, through a low-cost extender for building management systems (BMS).
- **PARITY** will integrate IoT and blockchain technologies to deliver a market for automated flexibility exchange based on smart contracts.
- **SENDER** will develop energy service applications for DR and home-automation through co-creation processes with end-users. The solutions will collect and process consumption data to mirror buildings behaviours in digital twins.
- **DB4 energy** develops a marketplace for secure data flows between energy data providers and solution providers, resulting in new data-driven business models and consumer participation in energy balancing. The demonstrators include buildings.
- **PLATOON** develops and deploys distributed edge processing and data analytics technologies for optimized real-time energy system management. Smart buildings are addressed in two pilots: operation performance of an [office building](#) in France and energy efficiency and predictive maintenance of a [smart tertiary building](#) in Spain.

Regarding **interoperability issues**, the following projects should be mentioned:

- **HOLISDER** develops an interoperable framework for DR optimization
- **PHEONIX**, **INTERCONNECT** and **TABEDE** develop solutions under the focus of full interoperability.
- **OPEN-DEI** conducts a cross-project analysis of Reference Architectures and Open Platforms, in particular within Large Scale Pilots focusing on the digitalisation of the energy system such as **INTERCONNECT** and **PLATOON**.

Figure 12: EC-funded projects screened for this White Paper

3.5. Other initiatives and innovations

Name of initiative / innovation	Weblink	Relevant inputs
CityGML	https://www.ogc.org/standards/citygml	To reach a common definition of the basic entities, attributes, and relations of a 3D city models with respect to the cost-effective sustainable maintenance of 3D city models, allowing the reuse of the same data in different application fields.
D-COM network	https://www.dcom.org.uk	The D-COM network is led by Cardiff University and was formed to drive forward the adoption of the digitization of regulations, requirements and compliance checking systems in the built environment.
AIOTI (Alliance for the IoT Innovation)/WG3 semantic interoperability group	https://aioti.eu/wg_ene_rgy/ https://aioti.eu/wg_buildings/	<p>AIOTI Working Group ENERGY. The working group supports the different Directorates of the European Commission in delivering workshops and policy papers on “Open Energy Marketplaces” activities linked to digitalisation in Energy Sector, P2P energy and role of blockchain and smart contracts. It also ensure coordination with ENTSO-E. KIC Innoenergy, ETIP-SNET and Sustainability Lab Bocconi.</p> <p>AIOTI Working Group BUILDING. The working group:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gathers innovation requirements from BMS vendors, real estate developers, operators, landlords, occupants ▪ Investigates the link between the building and the Grid through collaboration other groups and stakeholders ▪ Identify current regulatory initiatives ▪ Interact with Standardisation and Policy Groups for addressing data issues (privacy, ownership, protection...) ▪ Describe how IoT can be introduced by enhancing existing BMS and how to enable interaction across the different functions within the building (lighting, HVAC, shades, access control)
BuildingSMART International Solution & Standards Program	https://www.buildingsmart.org/standards/	World-wide industry body developing open neutral standards to support open digital ways of working for the built asset industry. The owner and developer of the IFC Schema and its related ecosystem including digital data dictionary and use case management services
Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)	https://smartreadinessindicator.eu/	Detailed in previous section.
Norwegian project FlexBuild (2019-2023)	https://www.sintef.no/projectweb/flexbuild/	Analysis of end-user flexibility in buildings and how this affects the rest of the energy system. Thermal flexibility such as cargo relocation, local heat storage and replacement of panel heaters with other heating technologies - district heating, heat pump, bioenergy - and electrical flexibility made available via building-integrated solar power, batteries and electric vehicles, will be analyzed in interaction with each other.

3.6. Lessons learnt

- For all **buildings**, Demand Response using a price signal (peak/off-peak, or blue/white/red, etc.) is already implemented in many countries and highly mature. However, for more advanced demand-response (not only ON-OFF) and a real-time flexibility market, maturity is lacking.
- Also, there is a significant lack of maturity on how to measure, track and prove how much flexibility has indeed been activated.
- For residential buildings, DR tools - such as potential flexibility forecast and fine energy management - are under development and pilot phases, but there is no consolidated return on experience yet.
- Same goes for RES (in particular PV) and storage controls in buildings for grid services.
- There is still some lack of standardisation in modelling the different smart assets on the way to provide their available flexibility.
- Also, there is a lack of commercial business models for the participation of small-scale residential buildings.

Illustration of lessons learnt: the FLEXCoop project

In the FLEXCoop project, the contribution of smart assets (HVAC and domestic hot water systems) with their available demand flexibility in innovative business models was tested. The overall framework was performed in a fully automated way, fully preserving end-users' comfort needs and preferences. A data driven measurement and verification framework - based on the IPMVP 2.0 methodology - was established to ensure the prompt valuation of the flexibility as provided by the different smart assets. One key remark of the project was the lack of standardization in the field of smart devices. There is no unified approach on modelling the different smart assets on the way to provide their available flexibility. On the other hand, the lack of viable business models is a key lesson learnt. While there is an ongoing discussion about the value of aggregation and flexibility, there are still missing commercial business models to promote the participation of small scale residential smart assets in demand side flexibility related services.

Identified mitigation measures regarding specific lacks:

- **Lack of standardized measurement and verification framework:** in order to properly assess the value of flexibility, a fair and transparent measurement and verification framework needs to be established that will facilitate the accurate calculation of the available flexibility.
- **Lack of clear separation of business roles acting in the electricity market:** one of the main bottlenecks towards the provision of flexibility is the lack of transparency among the different business actors. Different collaboration schemes are available in literature, but a standardized approach needs to be defined in order to clearly separate the roles and responsibilities among the different business entities.
- **Lack of standardization to avoid value stacking:** value stacking of flexibility is among the critical parameters that needs to be considered. The establishment of local flexibility marketplaces will ensure that value stacking is thoroughly considered in the analysis.

4. Barriers and drivers

4.1. Barriers

The table below synthesises the main barriers identified to the deployment of smart buildings providing flexibility services to the grid.

ECONOMIC	1. Lack of viable business models that really incentivize and remunerate the building occupants	} <i>Top barriers according to the Task Force</i>
VALUE CHAIN	2. Lack of readiness of industrial players including grid operators	
	3. Lack of technical and economic scalability of technologies (too customised, heavy human interventions required)	
REGULATION	4. Lack of standardization among smart devices and how they are modeled	
	5. GDPR and data privacy issues	
SOCIAL	6. Heterogeneity of national regulatory frameworks with regards to electricity markets and end-user participation	
	7. Lack of awareness of the functionalities and benefits of a grid-interactive building by the building end users	
TECHNICAL	8. Lack of interoperability of solutions as of today	

Figure 13: Overview of main barriers to the provision of power flexibility by smart buildings

Complementary information on specific barriers:

- Scalability - connectivity costs, availability: at the moment integration is obtained through highly customized interventions, with heavy human interaction. This is a barrier for the scalability of the technology. Interoperability is essential for a seamless communication among multiple services. The system should be highly scalable, accommodating increasing number of devices and services in the future both within a building and between buildings. It must also scale cost-effectively from the largest buildings to the smallest.
- Interoperability: as studied by TNO’s report on interoperability²¹, “the IT infrastructure to demand-side flexibility is covered by three different industries that all have separately developed technology and standards, i.e., the Utility industry, the Telecom industry and the Home appliances industry. Originated for different purposes and in different context, the communication standards from these industries are not necessarily aligned, leading to barriers in the seamless flow of data in the DSF infrastructure.”
- Customers’ awareness and motive: “The implementation of energy-efficiency programs, demand response, and outage-management applications will be effectively achieved through active customer participation in the system” (Gungor et al., 2012). Today, one of the main barriers is still the lack of awareness the functionalities and the benefits a smart grid can guarantee.

²¹ TNO, ESMIG, DNV-GL. 2018. Study on ensuring interoperability for enabling Demand Side Flexibility (DSF).

- Cost-effectiveness / market failure: in general, incentives should be used only when there are externalities or other market failures that justify their use as a tool to maximize societal benefits.
- Policies: smart grid policies are often developed and set forth by national governments in these countries but often fail or do not reach the success they aim to achieve.
- During the consultation phase, some feedback insisted on the missing access to near-real-time (i.e. very low delay) measurement data with high time resolution. Indeed, the required sensors are rarely installed, the digital infrastructure for data collection and sharing is poor/non-existing and often creates significant delays, data storage is expensive, and data access is hardly offered to third parties.

4.2. Drivers

The table below synthesises the main drivers identified to support the deployment of grid-interactive buildings.

VALUE CHAIN	1. Strong requirements faced by grid operators to integrate more renewable electricity in the grid, coupled with new types of loads (e-V) providing new flexibility sources	} Top drivers according to the Task Force
REGULATION & STANDARDS	2. Regulation allowing the development of local energy communities, self-consumption, demand-side flexibility	
	3. Regulatory constraints on data interoperability, transparent data access, data privacy, that will ensure privacy-friendly energy data exchange	
ECONOMIC	4. Financial incentives such as dynamic tariffs for consumers or the increase of CO2 emission rights price	
	5. Smart buildings becoming an investment opportunity for non-financial actors, such as private persons or companies	
SOCIAL	6. The willingness of citizens to reduce their environmental impact (from active consumer, to prosumer, to energy communities)	
TECHNICAL	7. New means and opportunities offered by communication automation & control technologies (from end user phone, to home appliances, to RES/storage devices, to smart grid)	
	8. The ongoing development and demonstration of interoperability-focused architectures, paving the way to standardization (connect any smart appliance to any service)	

Figure 14: Overview of main drivers supporting the deployment of flexibility services by smart buildings to the power network

Value Chain

When considering the whole value chain, smart buildings have demonstrated their ability to offer smart services and are therefore more and more recognized as potential flexibility providers. Aggregators and related energy service providers now have to take benefits from this position by developing relevant and valuable flexibility services.

In addition, energy grid operators are facing a strong requirement to host an increasing amount of Distributed Energy Resources and new energy consumers such as EVs, making flexibility increasingly relevant to support these needs with limited investment to grid reinforcement.

Regulatory

Several drivers also come from the regulation:

- Regulation is moving forward, allowing the development of local energy communities, self-consumption and flexibility markets.
- Regulation is more and more promoting demand-side flexibility from prosumers.
- Articles 23 and 24 of the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944 define interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to data, allowing the development of new data-based energy services.
- GDPR allows privacy-friendly energy data exchange.

Financial

From a financial perspective, the main drivers are:

- The development of dynamic tariffs, allowing consumers to easily reduce their energy bill by adopting flexibility-oriented behavioural patterns.
- Smart buildings become an investment opportunity for non-financial actors, such as private persons or companies.
- The increase of the CO2 emission allowance price supports the willingness to invest in efficiency and flexibility to avoid increasing electricity costs.

Social

The main driver from the social perspective is the willingness of certain citizens to reduce their environmental impact. These “active consumers” accept to change their habits to optimize the overall efficiency of the energy system and support the integration of renewables. Based on this dynamic, energy communities that include one or several smart buildings, are developing quite fast, gathering several actors to optimize together their energy consumption (and production) and possibly offer services to the grid.

Technical

From a technical perspective, the main drivers are:

- The wide deployment of new telecommunication networks - such as 5G, FTTH or LPWAN - eases the connection of home appliance to aggregator and energy service providers.
- Interoperability-focused architecture is being developed and demonstrated, paving the way to standardized approaches allowing to connect any smart appliance to any service.
- Models and digital twins allow to provide increasingly accurate flexibility forecasting.
- Through the combined management of heat, gas and electricity energy consumption, buildings enable sector coupling.

5. Research and Innovation Gaps

5.1. Research and development gaps

Additional research is needed on following topics:

- Further **integrate the different technologies** (sensors, storage, connectivity, software) – but to a certain extent to be identified: what is the optimal level of bundling (vs proliferation of solutions)?

- Explore **multi sided market** approaches, from consumer level to local service providers, aggregator. This implies bidirectional flows (from service provider to end-users and vice versa).
- **Assess the value of flexibility for buildings as flexibility provider:** further demonstration of demand response programmes at building level, validation of the level of flexibility delivered, determination of its value for the grid.
- In connection to previous point, explore - technical and economically - the contribution of **storage and electric vehicles** as components of the smart building providing flexibility.
- **Investigate how to collect and store detailed sub-metering data** with high resolution for different building typologies. In this topic also GDPR-issues will be important.
- **Investigate the automation level** (SRI) required for buildings to be able to provide flexibility services, and how to take existing buildings to this level.

5.2. Go-to-market gaps

Certification and standardisation:

- Development of a **flexibility certification scheme at EU level:** flexibility certification should become part of the overall building performance certification methods. Such certification scheme should allow to quantify the flexibility potential of the building; and validate the compatibility and relevance of each smart building to contribute to each type of flexibility (e.g. frequency support, congestion management, balancing, ...), depending on the smart building capabilities and characteristics.
- Common and harmonised definitions of flexibility products should facilitate the development of a certification scheme.
- **Further standardisation of protocols to exchange flexibility between buildings and grid operators** (including through flexibility aggregators). This includes the harmonization of existing standards on building level flexibility between member States.
- **Standardisation in the control of flexibility assets** within buildings: this includes the standardisation of home appliances connection and of protocols to control devices inside the buildings.
- **Standardisation in contracts:** the grid connection and exploitation dimensions for prosumers should be a standardised part in the energy supply contract.

Regulation:

- Build **new market regulation** to enable flexibility services and local energy markets. New market agents have to be defined and regulated, i.e. flexibility aggregator, and conflicts with current market participants have to be identified and solved. Regulation should also support the above-mentioned proposal of flexibility assessment and certification scheme.
- EU-wide harmonization of the regulation, and the way it is implemented in each Member State. In particular, **regulation in border areas** should allow flexibility exchange among countries.
- Investigate the issues of **ethics and artificial intelligence** applied to building flexibility services, in relation to the AI regulatory framework that the EC is designing.

Scaling up and industrialization:

- Consider the building flexibility services **at building design stage**, in a standardised manner. This also includes the process of end-user involvement in the design phase to ensure their future engagement for flexibility.
- **Regulatory sandboxes** to allow checking new business models and regulations in relevant environment involving real buildings and occupants (see the above-mentioned gap about new regulatory needs)
- Develop and deploy **ICT platforms** allowing to support a wide range of devices and services in an interoperable way, with limited additional cost
- **Design technologies** / equipment / hardware / IT so they include options for flexibility (i.e. no further investment / updates of technologies when connected to grid).
- **Define incentives to help early adopters to support the higher cost of new technologies** (while the followers will benefit from lower prices due to market expansion)
- **Explore the value of predictive maintenance** services attached to the smart building

6. Conclusions and next steps

This document formalises the collaborative work performed by the members of SmartBuilt4EU task force 3, on a voluntary basis, during the period March - June 2021. It also integrates the feedback collected during 1) a peer review conducted by VITO in June 2021, and 2) an open consultation process during in July – August 2021. Based on an analysis of the state of the art and the identification of barriers and drivers, the main objective of this paper is to detect some Research and Innovation gaps that still need to be addressed in the coming years in order to foster the further integration of smart buildings into the electricity networks. This White Paper will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda that the SmartBuilt4EU consortium will present to the European Commission.

Task Force 3 will investigate two more topics during 2021 – 2022: next topic, starting October 2021, will focus on **smart buildings as enabler of new energy practices and communities**.

If you have some expertise to share on this topic, you are invited to join the task force and contribute to the next White Paper (contact detail below).

To receive the updates on the SmartBuil4EU task forces, White Papers and events, please register here:
<https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/join-our-community/>

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